

Durability of Mortar in Presence of Rice Husk Ash

Md. Harunur Rashid, Md. Keramat Ali Molla, Tarif Uddin Ahmed

Abstract—The purpose of this paper is to investigate the durability of cement mortar in presence of Rice Husk Ash (RHA). The strength and durability of mortar with different replacement level (0%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25% and 30%) of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) by RHA is investigated here. RHA was manufactured from an uncontrolled burning process. Test samples were prepared with river sand of FM 2.73. Samples were kept in controlled environment up to test time. The results show that addition of RHA was shown better results for 20% replacement level than OPC at 90 days. In durability test all samples passed for 20 cycles except 25% and 30% replacement level.

Keywords—Rice Husk Ash; durability; mortar, graded sand.

I. INTRODUCTION

RICE is the main crop in Bangladesh. There are main three biomass by product comes from rice viz., rice straw, rice shell and rice bran. Considerable efforts are being taken worldwide to utilize local natural waste and by product materials in making concrete, such as RHA as supplementary cementing materials to improve concrete properties (strength, durability etc.) [1]-[10].

Rice husk is the outer jacket of the grain of white rice with high concentration of silica. Generally this silica concentration is more than 80-88% [11]. After burning rice husk contributes 20% of its weight to Rice Husk ash [12]. According to Tashima RHA is a high pozzolanic material. [13].

A large number of researches have been conducted towards the utilization of waste materials. For the development work the utilization of blended cement is growing rapidly. Pozzolans from industrial and agricultural byproducts are receiving more attention due to their uses in concrete production which improve the concrete property, and reduce the negative environmental effects. According to Mehtha [14] when rice husk is burnt at temperatures lower than 700⁰ C, rice husk ash with cellular microstructure is produced and contains high silica content in form of non-crystalline or amorphous silica and can be used as supplementary cementitious materials. Some other researchers wrote that the lower boundary of the temperatures is 550⁰ C. [18], [19].

When the rice husk is converted to ash by uncontrolled burning generally ranging from 300⁰ to 450⁰ C, the ignition was not completed and considerable amount of unburnt carbon was found in the resulting ash [20], [21]. The reactivity of amorphous silica is directly proportional to the specific surface area of ash [22]. Some research paper discovers that not only temperature but time is also one of the factors for burning the rice husk to produce effective ash [18], [19]. For the case of uncontrolled burning specially heap burning, the burning time totally depends upon the ambient environment ie. temperature, humidity and wind speed. Now limited researches were conducted again with the rice husk ash collected from uncontrolled burning process [2].

In this work RHA was collected from an uncontrolled burning system, where temperature and time was not controlled. After completion of burning, husk ash was collected and grinded for 30 minutes and pass the ash through 200 no sieve. The passed ash was collected and use as RHA in this work. It was found that the amount of Silicon Oxide in this ash is 90.20%. The summation of Silicon Oxide (SiO₂), Iron Oxide (Fe₂O₃) and Aluminum Oxide (Al₂O₃) is 92.43% and according to ASTM C-618, if the sum of Silicon Oxide, Iron Oxide and Aluminum Oxide is more than 70% in a material, then the material would be declared as a pozzolanic material.

So this ash which used in this work is a pozzolanic material. Pozzolans show different durability properties with the cement and type of active silica present in their composition. The amount and fineness of pozzolans in cement are factors that affect the strength of concrete.

Mortar is one of the most important components of a structure which as a material resulting of the close mixture of sand (Fine Aggregate), a binder (Lime, Cement, etc) and water. To improve some properties of mortar some different products or additional constituents are mixed with it. At the beginning the admixtures are composed of natural substances and currently that are industrial by product.

The research program, partially described in this paper, was carried out to assess the durability of mortar obtained with partial cement replacements with Rice Husk Ash in different percentages.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Raw materials used in these experiments were ordinary Portland cement, rice husk ash, sand with FM 2.73 and water. The rice husk ash used in this work was collected from an open burning system, where the rice husk allowed to burn for about 72 hours. Ambient temperature at that time was recorded 14⁰ to 19⁰ C and the peak of the husk temperature was 422⁰ C. Husk was heaped in 2 m square and 0.4m in height. For burning the husk, some rice husk briquette was fired and placed in the heap at a depth of 200mm from top. After placing the burned coal the

central temperature of the heap was measured for 60 hours and the time temperature curve is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Time VS Temperature Curve

Materials

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), river sand with specific gravity of 2.64, unit weight 1.63 gm/cc, absorption capacity 2.95% and fineness modulus of 2.73, details of sand fineness modulus is listed in Table I. Rice husk ash collected from open burning system and water were used.

TABLE I
 FINENESS MODULUS OF SAND

Sieve size	Wt. retained (gm)	Cumulative Wt. ret. (gm)	Cumulative % Wt. ret.
#4	0	0	0
#8	22.5	22.5	4.5
#16	85.5	108	21.6
#30	179	287	57.4
#50	165	452	90.4
#100	41.5	493.5	98.7
Pan	5	-	-

Mix Proportion and Curing

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) was replaced by different amount of RHA (0%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%) in dry condition. The mixture was thoroughly homogenized and kept in glass jar. Sample prepared with only OPC is called the controlled samples. The mix designations are in Table II. For preparing the sample sand to binder ration was 1:3.0 by weight of materials.

TABLE II
 MIX CONSTITUENTS AND DESIGNATION

Mix designation	OPC (%)	RHA (%)
A0	100	0
A10	90	10
A15	85	15
A20	80	20
A25	75	25
A30	70	30

The mortar was mixed in laboratory at $22 \pm 2^{\circ}$ C. After mixing, 50mm cubical specimens were cast from each mix for compressive strength and durability tests. After casting, all specimens were covered by poly paper in the casting room for 24 hours and then demolded and placed in a water bath ($22 \pm 2^{\circ}$ C) until the time of test.

III. TESTS

Consistency and Setting Time

Normal Consistency of OPC and RHA mixed cement was obtained according to ASTM C 187-98 [23]. The standard consistency was used to find out the initial and final setting time of the mortar.

Compressive Strength Test

After 3, 7, 28 and 90 day's the cured samples were removed from the curing pond and the area of loading face of cubes determined, and then placed at the center between plates of Universal Testing Machine.

Durability Test

The cured samples are immersed in water at a constant temperature of $20 \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ C for a period of 16 hours. The specimen was removed and placed in an oven pre-heated to 105° C to dry for six hours. Weights of the sample were measured. Samples were subjected to 20 such cycle.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Consistency and setting time

The percentage of cement replacement level by RHA against standard consistency graph Shown in Fig. 2. It was observed that the water demand for standard consistency linearly increases with an increase of cement replacement level by RHA.

Fig. 2 Normal Consistency verses % of cement replacement

The specific surface area of RHA is higher than the cement and the ashes are hygroscopic in nature, so needs more water.[14]

Variation in Initial and final setting time is shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. Maximum variation in initial setting time observed for 15% Cement Replacement Level (56.4%) and for 20% replacement level the variation is very close to the maximum (51.3%). For all replacement level the initial setting time observed is higher than the controlled mortar samples. The final setting time shows different results from the initial setting time. For all replacement level the final setting time shows decreasing nature with respect to OPC sample. From Fig. 4 it is observed that higher the replacement level shows lower the final setting

time. The final setting time measured for 0% and 30% cement replacement level is found to be 309 min and 222 min. respectively. These values are well within the permissible limits as per ASTM C 191-04. Bhanumathidas and Mehta [15], Ganesan et.al [16] and Cook [17] have also made similar observations.

Fig. 3 Initial and Final Setting time

Fig. 4 Variation in setting time with % of cement replacement

Compressive Strength

Compressive strength of mortar specimens are shown in Table III. comparison of the data for curing time of 3,7 and 28 days shows that the compressive strength of OPC mortar is higher than the others but at later age (90 days), the samples having 10%,15% and 20% RHA show better result than the OPC one. For 30% replacement level compressive strength at all test time was lower than the OPC samples.

The increase in strength may be due partially to the pozzolanic reaction and the presence of reactive silica in RHA as reported by many researchers [9], [16], [21], [23]-[25].

TABLE III
COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AT DIFFERENT AGES

Sample ID	RHA (%)	Strength (psi)			
		3 days	7 days	28 days	90 days
A0	0	1450	2137	3557	3671
A10	10	1150	2062	3579	3835
A15	15	1126	1994	3491	3729
A20	20	1217	1868	3326	3860
A25	25	1042	1806	3198	3405
A30	30	979	1575	2547	3061

Durability

The cured samples were taken at 90 days and perform durability test on it following the stated method. It was observed that A0, A10, A15 and A20 pass 20 cycles but A25 samples show crack at 18 cycles and some part of A30 samples was broken at 15 cycles. In Fig. 7 the amount of weight increases after 20 cycles of test is plotted. Here samples of A25 and A30 are not present. This happened due to the compactness of mortar in presence of RHA up to certain limit.

Fig. 7 Weight increase after Durability Test

V. CONCLUSION

This study indicates that up to 28 days OPC samples have higher strength than the RHA addition sample and at later age (90 day) the result is reverse up to 20% replacement level of OPC by Rice Husk Ash. Durability of mortar is also accepted for 20% replacement level.

It is concluded from the result that the mortar incorporating rice husk ash is more durable than OPC mortar up to 20% replacement level.

REFERENCES

- [1] Givi, A.N, S.A.Rashid, F.N.Aziz,M.A.M.Saleh, " Contribution of Rice Husk Ash to the properties of Mortar and Concrete: A Review" , Journal of American Science; 6(3),2010, pp. 157-165.
- [2] Chindaprasirt, P., and S.Rukzon, "Strength, porosity and corrosion resistance of ternary blend Portland cement, rice husk ash and fly ash mortar", Construction and Building Materials. 22(8):2008; pp 1601-1606.
- [3] Chindaprasirta, P., P. Kanchandaa, A.Sathonsaowaphaka, and H.T. Caob, "Sulfate resistance of blended cements containing fly ash and rice husk ash", Construction and Building Materials. 21(6): 2007; pp-1356-1361.

- [4] Coutinho, J.S. "The combined benefits of CPF and RHA in improving the durability of concrete structures", *Cement and Concrete Composites*. 25(1): 2002; pp-51-59.
- [5] Della, V.P., I. Kuhn, D. Hotza, "Rice husk ash as an alternate source for active silica production", *Materials Letters*. 57(4):2002; pp- 818–821.
- [6] Feng, Q., Yamamichi, H., Shoya, M., and Sugita, S. "Study on the pozzolanic properties of rice husk ash by hydrochloric acid pretreatment". *Cement and Concrete Research*. 34(3): 2004; pp-521–526.
- [7] Habeeb, G.A., and Fayyadh, M.M. 'Rice Husk Ash Concrete: the Effect of RHA Average Particle Size on Mechanical Properties and Drying Shrinkage". *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 3(3): 2009; pp-1616-1622.
- [8] Mahmud, H.B., Majuar, E., Zain, M.F.M., and Hamid, N.B.A.A. "Mechanical Properties and Durability of High Strength Concrete Containing Rice Husk Ash". *Journal of advanced concrete technology*. 79(1): 2009; pp-21-30.
- [9] Mehta, P.K. "Rice Husk Ash - A unique supplementary cementing material Proceeding" *International Symposium on Advances in Concrete Technology*. Editor. Malhotra, V.M. Athens, Greece, 1992; pp-407- 430.
- [10] Yu, Q., Sawayama, K., Sugita, S., Shoya, M., and Isojima, Y. "The reaction between rice husk ash and Ca(OH)₂ solution and the nature of its product" *Cement and Concrete Research*. 29(1): 1999; pp-37–43.
- [11] Siddique, F. "Waste materials and by-products in concrete": with 174 tables. Springer Press. 2008.
- [12] Anwar, M., Miyagawa, T., and Gaweesh, M. "Using rice husk ash as a cement replacement material in concrete". In the Proceedings of the 2001 first international Ecological Building Structure Conference. 2001; pp. 671- 684.
- [13] Tashima, M.M., Silva, C.A.R., Akasaki, J.L., and Barbosa, M.B. 'The Possibility of Adding the Rice Husk Ash (RHA) to the Concrete'. In the Proceedings of the 2004 International RILEM Conference on the Use of Recycled Materials in Building and Structures. 2004; pp. 778 – 786.
- [14] Metha PK. The chemistry and technology of cement made from rice husk ash. UNIDO/ESCAP/RCTT. In: Proceeding of work shop on rice husk ash cement, Peshawar, Pakistan. Bangalore, India: Regional Center for Technology Transfer; 1979. p. 113–22.
- [15] Bhanumathidas N, Mehta PK. Concrete mixtures made with ternary blended cements containing y ash and rice husk ash. In: Malhotra VM, editor. International conference proceeding seventh CANMETChennai, India; 2004; 1:SP 199-22; p. 379–91.
- [16] K. Ganesan, K.Rajagopal, K. Thangavel, "Rice husk ash blended cement: Assessment of optimal level of replacement for strength and permeability properties of concrete" *Construction and Building Materials*. 2007.
- [17] Cook JD. Rice husk ash. In: Swamy RN, editor. *Concrete technology and design. Cement replacement materials*, vol. 3. London: Surrey University Press; 1986. p. 171–95.
- [18] Boating AA, Skeete DH. Incineration of rice hull for use as a cementitious materials; the Guyana experience. *Cement Concrete Res*.1990;20:795–802.
- [19] James J, Subba Rao M. Silica from rice husk through thermal decomposition. *Thermochim Acta*, Elsevier Science, Amsterdam; 1986; (97): p. 329–36.
- [20] Columna VB. The effect of rice hull ash in cement and concrete mixes. M.Engg. Thesis, Asian Institute of Technology, 1974.
- [21] Al-Khalaf MN, Yousi. HA. Use of rice husk ash in concrete. *The Int J Cement Comp Light weight Concrete* 1984;6(4):241–8.
- [22] James J, Subba Rao M. Reactivity of rice husk ash. *Cement Concrete Res* 1986;16:296–302.
- [23] ASTM C 187-98 'Standard test method for Normal Consistency of Hydraulic Cement' ASTM International, 10th July, 1998.
- [24] Smith RG, Kamwanga GA. The use of rice husk for making a cementitious material. Use of vegetable plants and .bres as building materials. In: Joint symposium RILEM/CIB/CCL. Baghdad; 1986. p. 85–94.
- [25] Zhang MH, Malhotra VM. High-Performance concrete incorporating rice husk ash as supplementary cementing material. *ACI Mater J* 1996;93(6):629–36.
- [26] Mehta PK. Properties of blended cement made from rice husk ash. *ACI Mater J* 1977;74(9):440–2.